

What to Do if a Plan Does Not Comply with an HTN Model? – Pseudocode

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This document provides more details on the HTN plan correction algorithm presented in the paper:

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1 Pseudocode

1.1 Plan correction algorithm

The algorithm stores all state items generated so far in the set $states$. The completion relations (tuples (ps_1, ps_2, i) for each relation $completes(ps_1, ps_2, i)$ defined so far) are stored in the set $Completes$. The plan correction algorithm (Algorithm 1) first generates dummy starting state items that represent the decomposition of a dummy starting task s into each possible top-level task (lines 2 - 6). Then, the state item with the lowest total cost is removed from the priority queue and processed until a solution is found or the queue is empty (lines 3 - 25). If the next unprocessed subtask in a parsing state is an action, the state item is processed by the scanner (line 13; see Algorithm 2). If the next unprocessed subtask in a parsing state is an abstract task, the state item is processed by the predictor (line 15; see Algorithm 3). State items representing completed parsing states are processed by the completer (line 17; see Algorithm 4).

Candidate goal state items represent a completed decomposition of the dummy starting task s into a candidate top-level task, covering a prefix of the input plan (see lines 9 - 11). From such items, we attempt to extract grounded solutions by the procedure `Valid`, which computes for each such item all corresponding ground top-level task, the corresponding valid plans and the resulting true cost (equal to the real number of corrections) (see lines 20 and 26 and Algorithm 5). We can attempt to find a solution once the set of candidate goal items ($goals$) contains an item whose total cost is not higher than the minimum total cost in the queue (line 19). If the procedure `Valid` finds a solution with a true cost that satisfies this condition, we can terminate the algorithm and return this solution (line 22) as the items in the queue can only contribute to items with at least the same true cost (see Theorem 5). If no solution is found during the main loop, we compute the optimal solution after the queue is empty (see lines 26 - 30).

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Algorithm 1 Earley plan correction

Input: $\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mathcal{L}} = (X, V, K, Q, T, A, R, s_0, \rho)$ – totally ordered lifted HTN plan correction problem without empty rules, $\rho = \langle a_1, \dots, a_o \rangle$ – observed action sequence

Output: a goal parsing state with the lowest number of corrections, the resulting plan and number of corrections

Variables: $queue$ – priority queue of parsing state items, $goal^*$ – goal task with the lowest cost found so far (a tuple of a top-level task, a plan and a number of corrections), $cost^*$ – lowest solution cost found so far, $goals$ – candidate goals found so far, $cost(ps)$ and $inherited_cost(ps)$ – minimum number of corrections done before and in the decomposition of ps , $total_cost(ps) = inherited_cost(ps) + cost(ps)$, $state(ps)$ – the parsing state associated with the item ps , $states$ – all parsing states found so far, $Completes$ – a set of tuples (ps_1, ps_2, i) such that $completes(ps_1, ps_2, i)$

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1:  $Completes := \emptyset$ ,  $states := \emptyset$ ,  $queue :=$  an empty queue
2: for all  $t \in T$  do
3:    $ps_0 :=$  a new state item,  $state(ps_0) := (s \rightarrow \bullet t, 0, 0, \langle \rangle)$ 
4:    $cost(ps_0) := 0$ ,  $inherited\_cost(ps_0) := 0$ ,
    $total\_cost(ps_0) := 0$ 
5:    $states := states \cup \{ps_0\}$ , enqueue  $ps_0$  into  $queue$  with
   priority 0
6: end for
7: while  $queue$  is not empty do
8:    $ps :=$  dequeue state item with the lowest priority from  $queue$ 
9:   if  $state(ps) = (s \rightarrow t \bullet, 0, j, \langle j \rangle)$  then
10:     $goals := goals \cup \{ps\}$ 
11:   end if
12:   if  $state(ps) = (t \rightarrow$ 
13:      $t_1 \dots t_{j-1} \bullet t_j \dots t_n, p, q, \langle e_1, \dots, e_{j-2}, q \rangle)$  and  $t_j \in A_P^K$  then
14:      $Scanner(\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mathcal{L}}, \mathcal{G}, ps, queue, states, Completes)$ 
15:   else if  $state(ps) = (t \rightarrow$ 
16:      $t_1 \dots t_{j-1} \bullet t_j \dots t_n, p, q, \langle e_1, \dots, e_{j-2}, q \rangle)$  and  $t_j \in T_P^K$  then
17:      $Predictor(\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mathcal{L}}, \mathcal{G}, ps, queue, states, Completes)$ 
18:   else if  $state(ps) = (t \rightarrow t_1 \dots t_n \bullet, p, q, \langle e_1, \dots, e_{n-1}, q \rangle)$ 
19:     then
20:      $Completer(\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mathcal{L}}, \mathcal{G}, ps, queue, states, Completes)$ 
21:   end if
22:   if  $\min_{g \in goals} total\_cost(g) \leq \min_{ps \in queue} total\_cost(ps)$  then
23:      $goal^* = (t^*, \pi^*, cost^*) :=$ 
24:        $\underset{(t, \pi, corrections) \in \bigcup_{g \in goals} Valid(g), \mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mathcal{L}}, Completes, depth_{max}}}{\operatorname{argmin} corrections}$ 
25:     if  $cost^* \leq \min_{ps \in queue} total\_cost(ps)$  then
26:       return  $goal^*$ 
27:     end if
28:   end if
29: end while
30:  $goal^* = (t^*, \pi^*, cost^*) :=$ 
31:    $\underset{(t, \pi, corrections) \in \bigcup_{g \in goals} Valid(state(g), \mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mathcal{L}}, Completes, depth_{max})}{\operatorname{argmin} corrections}$ 
32: if no  $goal^*$  was found then
33:   return fail
34: end if
35: return  $goal^*$ 

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1.2 Scanner

The scanner (Algorithm 2) processes the items which represent states whose next unprocessed subtasks are actions. First, the scanner inserts the required action at the next available index in the input plan (lines 1 - 17). It is not necessary to insert the action also to indices to the right, deleting the actions in between, as action deletion can be performed by a next scanner operation if necessary. On line 1, the new parsing state is defined by moving the symbol \bullet to the right (marking the action as processed), preserving the start and end indices (as no action from the input plan was processed) and inserting the copy of the last end index to the list of subtask end indices. For the new parsing state, we only create a new state item if either no state item with the same parsing state has been created so far or there are already state items with the same parsing state, but their inherited costs are higher than the inherited cost of the currently processed state item. We need to generate state items with the lowest possible inherited costs in order to be able to record all possible completions in the completer (see section 1.4 for explanation). The inherited cost of the new state item will be equal to the inherited cost of the currently processed item and the cost of the action subtask will be equal to 1 as by inserting the action, we perform one correction (line 11). In addition, we define a dummy *completes* relation for the action (line 7) as these relations are later used during the solution computation (see section 1.5).

Then, the scanner attempts to unify the required action with all the remaining actions in the input plan, deleting the actions in between (lines 18 - 38). For each action unifiable with the required action, we proceed similarly as in action insertion: generating the new parsing state (line 20) and a new state item if the parsing state is new or if all items with the same parsing state have higher inherited costs (line 21) and recording the dummy completion (line 26). The new subtask cost is equal to the number of the deleted actions (line 30).

Algorithm 2 Scanner

Input: $\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mathcal{L}} = (X, V, K, Q, T, A, R, s_0, \rho)$ – totally ordered lifted HTN plan correction problem without empty rules, where $\rho = \langle a_1, \dots, a_n \rangle$, ps – parsing state item such that $state(ps) = (t_i \rightarrow t_1 \dots t_{j-1} \bullet t_j t_{j+1} \dots t_n, p, q, \langle e_1, \dots, q \rangle)$, where t_j is an action, *queue* – priority queue of parsing state items, *states* – all parsing state items generated so far, *Completes* – a set of tuples (ps_1, ps_2, i) such that $completes(ps_1, ps_2, i)$

- 1: $ps_2 := (t \rightarrow t_1 \dots t_{j-1} t_j \bullet t_{j+1} \dots, p, q, \langle e_1, \dots, q, q \rangle)$
- 2: **if** $\forall \tilde{ps} \in states : state(\tilde{ps}) \neq ps_2$ **or** $inherited_cost(\tilde{ps}) > inherited_cost(ps)$ **then**
- 3: $\tilde{ps} :=$ a new state item
- 4: $state(\tilde{ps}) := ps_2$
- 5: $item_{dummy} :=$ a new state item
- 6: $state(item_{dummy}) := (t_j \rightarrow t_j \bullet, q, q, \langle q \rangle)$
- 7: $Completes := Completes \cup \{(ps', \tilde{ps}, l) | (ps', ps, l) \in Completes\} \cup \{(item_{dummy}, \tilde{ps}, j)\}$
- 8: **for all** $l \in [j - 1]$ **do**
- 9: $cost(\tilde{ps}, l) := cost(ps, l)$
- 10: **end for**
- 11: $cost(\tilde{ps}, j) := 1$
- 12: $cost(\tilde{ps}) := \sum_{1 \leq l \leq j} cost(\tilde{ps}, l)$
- 13: $inherited_cost(\tilde{ps}) := inherited_cost(ps)$
- 14: $total_cost(\tilde{ps}) := inherited_cost(\tilde{ps}) + cost(\tilde{ps})$
- 15: enqueue \tilde{ps} into *queue* with priority $total_cost(\tilde{ps})$
- 16: $states := states \cup \{\tilde{ps}\}$
- 17: **end if**
- 18: **for all** $k \in \{q + 1, \dots, n\}$ **do**
- 19: **if** a_k is unifiable with t_j **and** $\sigma = mgu(a_k, t_j)$ **then**
- 20: $ps_2 := (t\sigma \rightarrow t_1\sigma \dots t_{j-1}\sigma a_k \bullet t_{j+1}\sigma \dots, p, k, \langle e_1, \dots, q, k \rangle)$
- 21: **if** $\forall \tilde{ps} \in states : state(\tilde{ps}) \neq ps_2$ **or** $inherited_cost(\tilde{ps}) > inherited_cost(ps)$ **then**
- 22: $\tilde{ps} :=$ a new state item
- 23: $state(\tilde{ps}) := ps_2$
- 24: $item_{dummy} :=$ a new state item
- 25: $state(item_{dummy}) := (a_k \rightarrow a_k \bullet, q, k, \langle k \rangle)$
- 26: $Completes := Completes \cup \{(ps', \tilde{ps}, l) | (ps', ps, l) \in Completes\} \cup \{(item_{dummy}, \tilde{ps}, j)\}$
- 27: **for all** $l \in [j - 1]$ **do**
- 28: $cost(\tilde{ps}, l) := cost(ps, l)$
- 29: **end for**
- 30: $cost(\tilde{ps}, j) := k - q - 1$
- 31: $cost(\tilde{ps}) := \sum_{1 \leq l \leq j} cost(\tilde{ps}, l)$
- 32: $inherited_cost(\tilde{ps}) := inherited_cost(ps)$
- 33: $total_cost(\tilde{ps}) := inherited_cost(\tilde{ps}) + cost(\tilde{ps})$
- 34: enqueue \tilde{ps} into *queue* with priority $total_cost(\tilde{ps})$
- 35: $states := states \cup \{\tilde{ps}\}$
- 36: **end if**
- 37: **end if**
- 38: **end for**

1.3 Predictor

The predictor (Algorithm 3) processes items where the next unprocessed subtask is an abstract task. Unlike in the original Earley parser, when we are processing a predictor parsing state, completions for the next unprocessed task may have already been generated since we do not process parsing states in an order based on the last covered action, but based on their total costs. Therefore, the predictor first searches for such completions (lines 2 - 22). We consider only the items representing completed parsing states where the start index is equal to the end index of the currently processed parsing state and the root task is not a more general instantiation of the next unprocessed task. If the root task is a more general form of the next unprocessed task, the completion would be unnecessarily general and would result in an underestimated cost. A more specific prediction will be generated (if it does not already exist), which will eventually result in a more specific completion for the currently processed state. The suitable completions are processed in ascending order of their costs, which eliminates the necessity to decrease priorities of items in the priority queue since if the same state item is created multiple times within this loop, it is first generated with the lowest possible total cost.

If a suitable completion is found, the resulting parsing state is created by moving the symbol \bullet to the right, merging the instantiations of the next unprocessed subtask from the currently processed parsing state and the root task of the completed parsing state (via the most general unifier σ) and setting the end index to the end index from the completed parsing state (see line 3). Similarly as in the scanner, we create a new state item for the parsing state if either no item with the same parsing state exists or the parsing state was rediscovered with a lower inherited cost. The new state items generated within this loop are stored in the set *new* so that when a new completion is discovered, it is recognized and recorded (lines 19 - 21).

Finally, new predictions are generated (similarly as in the original Earley parser) for the next unprocessed task by enumerating all the lifted or partially instantiated decomposition rules from the definition of the plan correction problem and unifying them with the next unprocessed task (lines 23 - 34). Let us note that the predictions are always generated with the lowest possible inherited cost (see Lemma 3).

Algorithm 3 Predictor

Input: $C_{\mathcal{H}}^L = (X, V, K, Q, T, A, R, s_0, \rho)$ – totally ordered lifted HTN plan correction problem without empty rules, where $\rho = \langle a_1, \dots, a_o \rangle$, ps – a parsing state item such that $state(ps) = (t \rightarrow t_1 \dots t_{j-1} \bullet t_j t_{j+1} \dots t_n, p, q, \langle e_1, \dots, q \rangle)$, where t_j is an abstract task, *queue* – priority queue of parsing states, *states* – all parsing state items generated so far, *Completes* – a set of tuples (ps_1, ps_2, i) such that $completes(ps_1, ps_2, i)$

- 1: $new := \emptyset$
- 2: **for all** $(\hat{p}s, \sigma)$ such that $state(\hat{p}s) = (t' \rightarrow t'_1 \dots t'_m \bullet, q, r, \langle e'_1, \dots, r \rangle)$ **and** $\hat{p}s \in states$ **and** $(t' = t_j \text{ or } t_j \text{ is a more general form of } t')$ **and** $\sigma = mgu(t', t_j)$ in ascending order of $cost(\hat{p}s)$ **do**
- 3: $ps_2 := (t\sigma \rightarrow t_1\sigma \dots t_j\sigma \bullet t_{j+1}\sigma \dots t_n\sigma, p, r, \langle e_1, \dots, q, r \rangle)$
- 4: **if** $\forall \tilde{p}s \in states : state(\tilde{p}s) \neq ps_2$ **or** $inherited_cost(\tilde{p}s) > inherited_cost(ps)$ **then**
- 5: $\tilde{p}s :=$ a new state item
- 6: $state(\tilde{p}s) := ps_2$
- 7: $Completes := Completes \cup \{(ps', \tilde{p}s, l) \mid (ps', ps, l) \in Completes\}$
- 8: **for all** $i \in [j - 1]$ **do**
- 9: $cost(\tilde{p}s, i) := cost(ps, i)$
- 10: **end for**
- 11: $cost(\tilde{p}s, j) := cost(\hat{p}s)$
- 12: $cost(\tilde{p}s) := \sum_{1 \leq l \leq j} cost(\tilde{p}s, l)$
- 13: $inherited_cost(\tilde{p}s) := inherited_cost(ps)$
- 14: $total_cost(\tilde{p}s) := inherited_cost(\tilde{p}s) + cost(\tilde{p}s)$
- 15: $states := states \cup \{\tilde{p}s\}$
- 16: enqueue $\tilde{p}s$ into *queue* with priority $total_cost(\tilde{p}s)$
- 17: $Completes := Completes \cup \{(\hat{p}s, \tilde{p}s, j)\}$
- 18: $new := new \cup \{\tilde{p}s\}$
- 19: **else if** $\exists \tilde{p}s \in new : state(\tilde{p}s) = ps_2$ **then**
- 20: $Completes := Completes \cup \{(\hat{p}s, \tilde{p}s, j)\}$
- 21: **end if**
- 22: **end for**
- 23: **for all** $(t' \rightarrow \beta, \sigma)$ such that $(t' \rightarrow \beta[C] \in R$ **and** t' is unifiable with t_j **and** $\sigma = mgu(t', t_j)$ **do**
- 24: $ps_2 := (t'\sigma \rightarrow \bullet t'_1 \dots t'_m \sigma, q, \langle \rangle)$
- 25: **if** $\forall \hat{p}s \in states : state(\hat{p}s) \neq ps_2$ **then**
- 26: $\tilde{p}s :=$ a new state item
- 27: $state(\tilde{p}s) := ps_2$
- 28: $cost(\tilde{p}s) := 0$
- 29: $inherited_cost(\tilde{p}s) := total_cost(ps)$
- 30: $total_cost(\tilde{p}s) := inherited_cost(\tilde{p}s) + cost(\tilde{p}s)$
- 31: enqueue $\tilde{p}s$ into *queue* with priority $total_cost(\tilde{p}s)$
- 32: $states := states \cup \{\tilde{p}s\}$
- 33: **end if**
- 34: **end for**

1.4 Completer

State items representing completed parsing states are processed by the completer (Algorithm 4). First, the completer proceeds similarly as in the original Earley parser, generating new parsing states by using the currently processed completed state to decompose the next unprocessed abstract task in suitable items (lines 1 - 18). For completion, we consider state items representing parsing states where the next unprocessed task is not a more specific form of the root task of the currently processed completed parsing state (the reason is the same as in the predictor – see section 1.3), the end index is equal to the start index of the currently processed parsing state and the total cost is not smaller than the inherited cost of the currently processed state item. The last condition is necessary to ensure that by processing a state item, we cannot discover another state item with a lower total cost (Lemma 1). We can safely disregard such states as the scanner, predictor and completer generate copies of existing state items if they are rediscovered with a lower inherited cost and this copies will eventually be used to find the required completion in the completer or in the predictor. For each parsing state considered, the new parsing state is created (on line 2) by moving the symbol \bullet to the right and merging the instantiations of the parsing state and the currently processed parsing state (via the most general unifier σ). As in the scanner and predictor, we create a new state item for the new state if either no item with the same parsing state exists or the parsing state was rediscovered with a lower inherited cost. In this loop, we do not record completions for already existing states as this will be done in the second loop.

In the second loop (lines 19 - 28), the completer finds new completions for already existing state items. We utilize the list of subtask end indices and select all state items which contain a completed subtask which covers the same input subsequence as the currently processed state item and whose instantiation is not more general than the root task of the currently processed parsing state. We can safely disregard the states that do not satisfy the last condition as a more specific form of these parsing states was or will be generated by a more specific completion. We also disregard the states whose sum of their inherited cost and the costs of the subtasks preceding the relevant subtask is smaller than the inherited cost of the currently processed completed state item. Again, this condition is necessary to ensure that by processing a state item, we cannot discover another state item with a lower total cost (Lemma 1) and the other items can be safely disregarded as items with the lowest possible inherited costs are created. Here, it is possible that the total cost of the affected state item is decreased by adding the new completion (see line 21). Then, we need to remove it from the queue and enqueue it again with the new priority. Let us note that a state item is never processed before its lowest possible total cost is found (see Lemma 2).

Algorithm 4 Completer

Input: $\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mathcal{L}} = (X, V, K, Q, T, A, R, s_0, \rho)$ – totally ordered lifted HTN plan correction problem without empty rules, where $\rho = \langle a_1, \dots, a_o \rangle$, ps – a parsing state item representing a completed parsing state such that $\text{state}(ps) = (t \rightarrow t_1 \dots t_n \bullet, p, q, \langle e_1, \dots, q \rangle)$, $queue$ – priority queue of parsing state items, $states$ – all parsing state items generated so far, $Completes$ – a set of tuples (ps_1, ps_2, i) such that $\text{completes}(ps_1, ps_2, i)$

- 1: **for all** (\hat{ps}, σ) such that $\hat{ps} \in states$ **and** $(\text{state}(\hat{ps}) = (t' \rightarrow t'_1 \dots t'_{i-1} \bullet t'_i t'_{i+1} \dots t'_m, r, p, \langle e'_1, \dots, p \rangle), \sigma)$ **and** $(t'_i = t$ **or** t'_i is a more general form of $t)$ **and** $\sigma =$
- 2: $\text{mgu}(t'_i, t)$ **and** $\text{inherited_cost}(ps) \leq \text{total_cost}(\hat{ps})$ **do**
- 3: $ps_2 := (t' \sigma \rightarrow t'_1 \sigma \dots t'_i \sigma \bullet t'_{i+1} \sigma \dots t'_m \sigma, r, q, \langle e'_1, \dots, p, q \rangle)$
- 4: **if** $\forall \tilde{ps} \in states : \text{state}(\tilde{ps}) \neq ps_2$ **or** $\text{inherited_cost}(\tilde{ps}) > \text{inherited_cost}(ps)$ **then**
- 5: $\tilde{ps} :=$ a new state item
- 6: $\text{state}(\tilde{ps}) := ps_2$
- 7: $Completes := Completes \cup \{(ps', \tilde{ps}, l) \mid (ps', \tilde{ps}, l) \in Completes\}$
- 8: **for all** $j \in [i - 1]$ **do**
- 9: $\text{cost}(\tilde{ps}, j) := \text{cost}(\hat{ps}, j)$
- 10: **end for**
- 11: $Completes := Completes \cup \{(ps, \tilde{ps}, i)\}$
- 12: $\text{cost}(\tilde{ps}, i) := \text{cost}(ps)$
- 13: $\text{cost}(\tilde{ps}) := \sum_{1 \leq l \leq i} \text{cost}(\tilde{ps}, l)$
- 14: $\text{inherited_cost}(\tilde{ps}) := \text{inherited_cost}(\hat{ps})$
- 15: $\text{total_cost}(\tilde{ps}) := \text{inherited_cost}(\tilde{ps}) + \text{cost}(\tilde{ps})$
- 16: enqueue \tilde{ps} into $queue$ with priority $\text{total_cost}(\tilde{ps})$
- 17: $states := states \cup \{\tilde{ps}\}$
- 18: **end if**
- 19: **end for**
- 20: **for all** \hat{ps} such that $\text{state}(\hat{ps}) = (t' \rightarrow \dots t'_j \bullet \dots t'_m, r, s, \langle e'_1, \dots, s \rangle)$ **and** $\hat{ps} \in states$ **and** $\exists i : t'_i$ is a subtask in $\text{state}(\hat{ps})$ **and** $i \leq j$ **and** $(t'_i = t$ **or** t is a more general form of $t'_i)$ **and** $e'_i = q$ **and** $(i > 1$ **and** $e'_{i-1} = p$ **or** $i = 1$ **and** $r = p)$ **and** $\text{inherited_cost}(ps) \leq \text{inherited_cost}(\hat{ps}) + \sum_{1 \leq l < i} \text{cost}(\hat{ps}, l)$ **do**
- 21: $Completes := Completes \cup \{(ps, \hat{ps}, i)\}$
- 22: **if** $\text{cost}(ps) < \text{cost}(\hat{ps}, i)$ **then**
- 23: $\text{cost}(\hat{ps}, i) := \text{cost}(ps)$
- 24: $\text{cost}(\hat{ps}) := \sum_{1 \leq l \leq m} \text{cost}(\hat{ps}, l)$
- 25: $\text{total_cost}(\hat{ps}) := \text{inherited_cost}(\hat{ps}) + \text{cost}(\hat{ps})$
- 26: remove \hat{ps} from $queue$
- 27: enqueue \hat{ps} into $queue$ with priority $\text{total_cost}(\hat{ps})$
- 28: **end if**
- 29: **end for**

1.5 Solution computation

The procedure Valid (Algorithm 5) computes for a given candidate goal state item a set of tuples of the corresponding ground top-level tasks, plans and the true number of corrections, representing valid solutions to the HTN plan correction problem. The procedure computes all groundings of the top-level task. Ground abstract subtasks are computed by the procedure Decomposable (Algorithm 6). The procedure Decomposable returns a set of tuples of a ground task, a plan, start and end indices, constraints propagated from the decomposition rules and the number of corrections to decompose the task.

For each possible solution, we verify whether the resulting plan is valid (with respect to the state transition function γ , known from classical planning, that defines how effects of actions modify states) and whether the constraints propagated from subtask decomposition rules are satisfied (line 7). For valid solutions, we compute the resulting number of corrections by adding the sum of the number corrections of subtasks and the length of the unused suffix of the input plan that needs to be deleted (lines 3 - 10).

The procedure Decomposable (Algorithm 6) proceeds in a similar manner. For the currently processed abstract subtask, it enumerates all its possible decompositions defined by the *completes* relations (see line 5), grounding abstract subtasks recursively. Partially instantiated actions are defined by the corresponding dummy *completes* relations, which also determine the cost of the correction required to obtain an action (see lines 11 - 15). In addition, for each combination of ground subtask solutions, we create the set of rule constraints that will be propagated to the procedure Valid (line 23).

Algorithm 5 Valid

Input: ps – state item such that $\text{state}(ps) = (s \rightarrow t\bullet, 0, e, \langle e \rangle)$, $\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mathcal{L}} = (X, V, K, Q, T, A, R, s_0, \rho)$ – totally ordered lifted HTN plan correction problem without empty rules, where preconditions and effects of actions define the transition function γ and $\rho = \langle a_1, \dots, a_o \rangle$, *Completes* – a set of tuples (ps_1, ps_2, i) such that $\text{completes}(ps_1, ps_2, i)$, *max_depth* – maximum allowed search depth

Output: a set of tuples of top-level tasks, the corresponding plans that are solutions to $\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mathcal{L}}$ and the number of corrections

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1: Ground := Decomposable( $t, \mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mathcal{L}}, \{c = (ps', ps, 1) | c \in$ 
   Completes $\}, \text{Completes}, 1, \text{max\_depth}$ )
2: Solutions :=  $\emptyset$ 
3: for all  $(t', \pi = \langle a_1, \dots, a_k \rangle, C, \text{corr}) \in \text{Ground}$  do
4:   for all  $i \in [k]$  do
5:      $s_i := \gamma(s_{i-1}, \pi_i)$ 
6:   end for
7:   if  $\forall i \in [k] : \pi_i$  is applicable in  $s_{i-1}$  and  $\forall (l, p) \in C : p \in s_i$ 
   then
8:     Solutions := Solutions  $\cup (t', \pi, \text{corr} + o - e)$ 
9:   end if
10: end for
11: return Solutions

```

Algorithm 6 Decomposable

Input: t – abstract task, $\mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mathcal{L}} = (X, V, K, Q, T, A, R, s_0, \rho)$ – totally ordered lifted HTN plan correction problem without empty rules, where preconditions and effects of actions define the transition function γ and $\rho = \langle a_1, \dots, a_o \rangle$, *CompletingStates* – set of parsing states possibly decomposing t , *Completes*, *depth* – decomposition tree depth, *max_depth* – maximum allowed search depth

Output: a set of tuples of grounded tasks t decomposable via parsing states from *CompletingStates*, the corresponding found plans, start and end indices of actions into which t is decomposable, a set of indexed rule constraints, where (i, p) indicates that $p \in s_i$ and the number of corrections

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1: if  $\text{depth} > \text{max\_depth}$  then
2:   return  $\emptyset$ 
3: end if
4: Solutions :=  $\emptyset$ 
5: for all  $\text{state}(ps) = (t \rightarrow t_1 \dots t_k \bullet, r, s, \langle e_1, \dots, s \rangle)$  such that
    $ps \in \text{CompletingStates}$  do
6:   GroundSubtasks := array of length  $k$ 
7:   for  $i \in [k]$  do
8:     if  $t_i \in T_P^K$  then
9:       GroundSubtasks[ $i$ ] := Decomposable( $t_i, \mathcal{C}_{\mathcal{H}}^{\mathcal{L}}, \{c =$ 
    $(ps', ps, i) | c \in$ 
   Completes $\}, \text{Completes}, \text{depth} + 1, \text{max\_depth}$ )
10:    else
11:      action_state :=  $(t_i \rightarrow t_i \bullet, p, q, \langle q \rangle)$  such that
    $(\bar{ps}, ps, i) \in \text{Completes}$  and  $\text{state}(\bar{ps}) = (t_i \rightarrow$ 
    $t_i \bullet, p, q, \langle q \rangle)$ 
12:      if  $p = q$  then
13:        GroundSubtasks[ $i$ ] :=  $\{(t_i, \langle t_i \rangle, p, q, \emptyset, 1)\}$ 
14:      else
15:        GroundSubtasks[ $i$ ] :=  $\{(t_i, \langle t_i \rangle, p, q, \emptyset, q - p - 1)\}$ 
16:      end if
17:    end if
18:  end for
19:   $r := (t \rightarrow t_1 \dots t_k, C) \in R$  {the corresponding rule from  $R$ }
20:  for all
    $(\sigma, \pi_1, \dots, \pi_k, p_1, \dots, p_k, q_k, C_1, \dots, C_k, \text{corr}_1, \dots, \text{corr}_k)$ 
   such that  $(t'_1, \pi_1, p_1, q_1, \text{corr}_1) \in$ 
   GroundSubtasks[1], ...,  $(t'_k, \pi_k, p_k, q_k, \text{corr}_k) \in$ 
   GroundSubtasks[ $k$ ] and  $\sigma = \text{mgu}(t \rightarrow t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k, t \rightarrow$ 
    $t'_1 t_2 \dots t_k, t \rightarrow t_1 t'_2 \dots t_k, \dots, t \rightarrow t_1 t_2 \dots t'_k)$  do
21:     $\pi := \pi_1 + \pi_2 + \dots + \pi_k$ 
22:    for all  $\sigma'$  such that  $r\sigma\sigma'$  and  $\pi\sigma\sigma'$  is ground do
23:       $C' := \bigcup_{l \in [k]} C_l \cup \bigcup_{\text{before}(t_i, p) \in C\sigma\sigma'} \{(p_i, p)\} \cup$ 
    $\bigcup_{\text{after}(t_i, p) \in C\sigma\sigma'} \{(q_i, p)\} \cup$ 
    $\bigcup_{\text{between}(t_i, t_m, p) \in C\sigma\sigma', p_i < l < q_m} \{(l, p)\}$ 
24:      Solutions :=
   Solutions  $\cup (t\sigma\sigma', \pi\sigma\sigma', j, q_k, C', \sum_{1 \leq i \leq k} \text{corr}_i)$ 
25:    end for
26:  end for
27: end for
28: return Solutions

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2 Properties

In the following proofs, the symbol β is sometimes used for brevity to represent an arbitrary sequence of subtasks.

Lemma 1. *Let ps be a state item and let ps' be a state item that is newly created or whose total cost is decreased during processing of ps . Then $\text{total_cost}(ps) \leq \text{total_cost}(ps')$ after ps is processed.*

Proof. The proof is straightforward for scanning, where ps' can only be a newly created state item. The total cost of the new state item ps' clearly cannot be less than the total cost of ps as we only add the number of corrections to the total cost of ps . Then, $\text{total_cost}(ps') = \text{total_cost}(ps) + 1$ if a new action was inserted, or $\text{total_cost}(ps') = \text{total_cost}(ps) + k$ ($k \geq 0$), when k actions were deleted.

During prediction, ps' can also be only a newly created state item, created either by completion or by prediction. First, consider the prediction. Then $\text{total_cost}(ps') = \text{inherited_cost}(ps') = \text{total_cost}(ps)$. Second, consider completion in the predictor. Similarly as in the scanner, we only move \bullet to the right as we add a new completion. Then, if ps' is a new state item created by this completion, clearly $\text{total_cost}(ps') \geq \text{total_cost}(ps)$ since $\text{total_cost}(ps') = \text{total_cost}(ps) + \text{cost}(ps'')$ and $\text{cost}(ps'') \geq 0$, where ps'' is the item used for completion.

Now we will prove the lemma for completion. Let ps be a completed state. First, let us assume that the completer creates a new state ps' from ps and ps'' . Since $\text{inherited_cost}(ps) \leq \text{total_cost}(ps'') = \text{inherited_cost}(ps'') + \sum_{l < k} \text{cost}(ps'', l)$, $\text{total_cost}(ps') = \text{total_cost}(ps'') + \text{cost}(ps) \geq \text{inherited_cost}(ps) + \text{cost}(ps) = \text{total_cost}(ps)$.

Second, if the completer does not create a new state but instead decreases the total cost of the existing state ps' , then the completer decreases $\text{cost}(ps', k)$ to $\text{cost}(ps)$. Since $\text{inherited_cost}(ps) \leq \text{inherited_cost}(ps') + \sum_{l < k} \text{cost}(ps', l)$, then, after processing ps , $\text{total_cost}(ps') \geq \text{inherited_cost}(ps') + \sum_{l < k} \text{cost}(ps', l) + \text{cost}(ps', k) \geq \text{inherited_cost}(ps) + \text{cost}(ps) = \text{total_cost}(ps)$. \square

Lemma 2. *A state item is not processed until its lowest possible total cost is discovered. In addition, a state item ps is not processed until the lowest possible value of $\text{total_cost}(p\hat{s})$, where $\text{state}(p\hat{s}) = \text{state}(ps)$, is discovered.*

Proof. For contradiction, consider a parsing state item ps that was processed at a point where $\text{total_cost}(ps) = c$. Later, either the total cost of ps was decreased in the completer or another state item representing the same parsing state was discovered with a lower total cost.

Since, by Lemma 1, we cannot discover a parsing state with a lower cost by processing another parsing state with a higher cost, another state item ps'' exists such that $\text{total_cost}(ps'') \leq \text{total_cost}(ps') < \text{total_cost}(ps)$. To discover ps'' , we had to first discover another state with at most the same cost. This assumption can be applied recursively; therefore, there has to be a sequence of state items with total costs lower than ps that had to be discovered and processed before ps was processed with cost c , which is a contradiction. \square

Lemma 3. *Predictions are generated in ascending order of inherited costs. That is, let ps , where $\text{state}(ps) = (t \rightarrow \bullet\beta, i, i, \langle \rangle)$, be a state item generated by the predictor such that $\text{inherited_cost}(ps) = c$,*

then $\text{state}(ps)$ will never be rediscovered with an inherited cost $c' < c$.

Proof. For contradiction, consider the first situation where this proposition is violated. That is, let $\text{state}(ps)$ be first generated with total cost c from item ps' and then again with a cost $c' < c$ from a state item ps'' . By Lemma 1, to discover ps'' with its current total cost $\text{total_cost}(ps')$, we would have to first process a sequence of state items with at most the same total cost as ps'' before we process ps' with the total cost c (the argumentation is similar as in the proof of Lemma 2), which is a contradiction. \square

Lemma 4. *The last condition on lines 1 and 19 of Algorithm 4 is valid. That is, if it is not satisfied, the currently processed parsing state ps does not provide a decomposition of the subtask t'_i of the state item $p\hat{s}$ that could lead to a possible solution to the HTN plan correction problem that would not be found otherwise.*

Proof. If $\text{inherited_cost}(ps) > \text{inherited_cost}(p\hat{s}) + \sum_{1 \leq l < i} \text{cost}(p\hat{s}, l)$, the prediction predecessor of ps (the prediction $\text{state}(ps') = (t'' \rightarrow \bullet t''_1 \dots t''_m, p, p, \langle \rangle)$, where $t'' = t'_i$ or t'' is a more general form of t'_i , from which ps has been eventually generated) clearly had not been generated by the predictor during the processing of a predecessor of $p\hat{s}$ (see Lemma 3). Thus, there is another prediction representing the same decomposition (the prediction $\text{state}(ps'') = (t''' \rightarrow \bullet t'''_1 \dots t'''_m, p, p, \langle \rangle)$, where $t''' = t'_i$ or t''' is a more general form of t'_i and t''' can be a more general or a more specific form of t''), which was generated by the predictor while processing either a predecessor of $p\hat{s}$ or another parsing state and whose inherited cost is lower than the inherited cost of ps' . Since we preserve parsing states with the lowest inherited costs found so far, these three situations can occur:

- a successor of ps'' representing the same decomposition as ps was created and its total cost is lower than the total cost of ps ,
- a successor of ps'' representing the same decomposition as ps was or will be eventually created and its total cost is greater or equal to the total cost of ps , or
- a successor of ps'' will never be created.

Let us note that cases a) and b) can both occur as more successors of ps'' (with different instantiations of variables) can be found.

In the case a), the successor of ps'' had to be processed already before ps . Therefore, this completion has already been recorded for $p\hat{s}$. If ps represents a more general instantiation of ps'' , ps would not be suitable for completion as all successors of ps'' represent instantiations compatible with the prediction predecessor of $p\hat{s}$.

For the successors in b), the arguments are the same, but the successors may be processed later than ps , again resulting in no loss of information. If the total cost of such completion is greater than the total cost of ps , then we can assume that the lower cost associated with ps is not a suitable estimate for the completion of the state $p\hat{s}$ and should not be used to lower the cost of $p\hat{s}$.

If the situation in c) occurs, we can safely conclude that there is no solution that includes the variables from ps'' . Therefore, no instantiation of ps would result in a solution if ps was recorded as a completion for $p\hat{s}$. \square

Theorem 5. *The algorithm of Earley plan correction is sound, complete and optimal.*

Proof. Algorithm 1 is clearly sound as the procedures Valid and Decomposable check if all preconditions of all actions and all con-

straints of all decomposition rules are satisfied. Therefore, if the algorithm finds a solution, it is a task network that decomposes into a valid HTN plan.

There is a finite number of parsing states that can be generated by the algorithm; the states correspond to all combinations of all partially instantiated decomposition rules, all possible positions of \bullet in subtasks and start and end indices of the decomposition and end indices of decompositions of all subtasks (from 0 to the length of the observed action sequence).

However, more state items can represent the same parsing states. Nevertheless, a state item with an already existing parsing state is created only when a parsing state is rediscovered with a lower inherited cost. However, parsing states corresponding to predictions (that is, representing a decomposition $t \rightarrow \bullet t_1 \dots t_k$) are unique as predictions are always generated with the lowest possible inherited costs (see Lemma 3).

Additionally, when a state item is created with a non-unique parsing state, predictions will be generated only from one copy of the same state item and its descendant states. When two items with a different total cost represent the same parsing state, all their corresponding successor state items, created in the predictor or scanner by moving \bullet to the right and perhaps specializing the subtasks, will also correspond to the same parsing states. Therefore, these state items would generate also the same predictions, possibly with different costs. However, we only create predictions once and they are always generated with the lowest possible inherited cost (see Lemma 3). Thus, predictions will be generated only once for each position of \bullet in descendant parsing states of ps .

Although we cannot bound the number of state items by the number of all parsing states, we can bound it by the number of pairs (ps_1, ps_2) , where ps_2 is a parsing state and ps_1 is a prediction from which ps_2 was generated by scannings and completions (for predictions, we can use a dummy ps_1). Therefore, since the number of parsing states is finite, the number of state items is also finite.

Once a parsing state item is removed from the priority queue on line 8 of Algorithm 1, it is never enqueued again. Therefore, since the algorithm generates only a finite number of parsing state items and all parsing state items are processed at most once, if the termination of the procedures Valid and Decomposable is ensured by limiting the search depth, the algorithm of the Earley plan correction terminates. However, with iterative deepening, the algorithm may not terminate if no solution exists.

The scanner (Algorithm 2) eventually generates all plans that can be obtained by action insertion and action deletion from the input action sequence. Regarding action insertion, it is sufficient to insert the action at the given position (without deleting any actions). If the next scanner requires action deletion, it can delete the actions itself.

As we always use the most general unifier to determine the task instantiations of the new parsing state, all ground solutions can be extracted. The definition of the completer (Algorithm 4) and predictor (Algorithm 3) ensure that all the possible completing relations are recorded for all relevant parsing states. If a relevant completion is found before the parsing state is created, the predictor records all such relations upon the parsing state creation. Otherwise, the completer records the completing relations for all the already existing relevant states. Algorithm 4 sometimes disregard completions that could result in violation of Lemma 1; however, these items can be safely dismissed as there will eventually be a copy of each state item with the lowest possible inherited cost (see Lemma 4). Algorithm 5 and Algorithm 6 generate in a depth-first search manner all grounded solutions that satisfy action preconditions and rule constraints. To

conclude, if a solution exists and either a sufficient maximum search depth is selected or iterative deepening is implemented, the solution will be found; therefore, the algorithm is sound.

The algorithm halts when a solution is found such that its number of corrections is not higher than the total cost of any parsing states in the queue (see line 22 of Algorithm 1). At this point, it is clear that no better solution can be found since the state items in the queue cannot contribute to a solution with a total cost (see Lemma 1) and the total cost is a lower bound on the number of corrections. The number of corrections is correctly computed by adding the number of inserted actions, the number of actions deleted between the actions selected from the input sequence (see lines 11 - 15 of Algorithm 6) and the number of actions deleted at the end of the input sequence (see line 8 of Algorithm 5). Therefore, the algorithm is optimal (the algorithm finds a solution corresponding to the lowest possible number of corrections). \square